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A BRIEF TALK ON UZBEK FOLK FAIRY TALES

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ABSTRACT

Fairy tales are one of the early genres of folk literature, and Uzbek fairy tales are no exception. According to the content described, Uzbekistan's folk fairy tales can be divided into three categories: one is magic fairy tales; the other is animal fairy tales; and the third is social life fairy tales. The characters and animal images in these three types of fairy tales have their own characteristics, and there are many overlaps. This article reveals the rich national cultural charm behind the fairy tales by analyzing the content, types and image shaping of the three types of fairy tales.

Fairy tales are one kind of children's literature. The general storyline is magical and tortuous, vivid and simple, and often anthropomorphic descriptions of natural objects are more suitable for children's curious and imaginative characteristics. The vivid image is created through rich fantasy and exaggerated methods, and the twists and turns are moving. The simple and easy-to-understand language reflects real life, suppresses evil and promotes good, and fairy tales are indeed one of the most favorite literary works of children. Uzbek folk fairy tales have a typical Uzbek national style. This article will start with the content, classify Uzbek folk fairy tales, and analyze its content characteristics, character images and animal images.

1. Magical fairy tales

Among the many kinds of fairy tales, magical fairy tales are the oldest and the most famous. The world it presents is full of all kinds of mysterious characters and

weird animals. The protagonist is an omnipotent god who possesses superb skills, but also represents justice, kindness and truth, and can always defeat darkness, evil and lies. This kind of fairy tales usually use magic and anthropomorphic techniques to show the hero's bravery and wisdom, and some natural elements such as sunlight and wind are also used.

The protagonists in magical fairy tales have both characters and animals. Most of the characters are kenja botir (old and young hero), chol (old man), podshoh (king), yalmog'iz (old witch), dev, ajina (devil, evil spirit), pari (fairy), etc. Evil elves, demons, and old witches are usually symbols of evil, while fairies are symbols of goodness. They use magic to help the protagonist succeed. The protagonists of fairy tales show their wisdom through the tenacious struggle against evil forces. Especially the heroic growth experience of the protagonist in the fairy tale is also full of legends. The story

lines of magical fairy tales generally unfold on the journey, and the end of the story is usually an unsolved mystery. Numbers like 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 40 are often used to organize characters or develop a plot (such as three roads, three brothers, three sisters, three days and three nights, seven nobita, seven A fairy, seven heads, seven days and seven nights, 40 days and 40 nights, etc.).

There are also various animal images in magical fairy tales, such as: ot (horse), laylak (stork), maymun (monkey), to'ti (parrot), ajdar (dragon), kabutar (pigeon). The protagonist in the magic fairy tale helps them, and then they help the protagonist in order to express their gratitude. For example, they give the protagonist three feathers, when he encounters difficulties, he lights one of them, and they immediately come to help. For example, the fairy tale "Beat it, stick" tells a simple and poor old man who becomes rich with the help of a stork, and eventually becomes a king. Although the old man lives by hunting, he let go of the stork. In order to express his gratitude to the grandfather, the stork gives him a "Jar", "A Tablecloth" and "A Stick". After that, the old man obtains various wealth and becomes a king with the help of these gifts. Take another magical fairy tale called "Zumrad and Kimmat". This fairy tale tells about a little girl named Zumrad through her innocence and purity, friendliness, kindness, and helpful personality to achieve a happy life. She was often hardshipped by her stepmother, so she had to leave home. But she meets a conscientious old woman. With the help of the old woman, Zumrad lives a happy life with his father.

2. Animal fairy tales

Animal fairy tales are one of the oldest types of folklore. It originated from primitive animal myths, and echoes the myths of animal totems, the stories about birds and beasts, and legends about the relationship between gods and animals with divine nature.

Animal images in Uzbek fairy tales include: (bo'ri) wolf, (tulki) fox, (sher) lion, (quyon) rabbit, (qo'y) sheep, (xo'roz) rooster, (it) dog, etc.

Animal fairy tales include not only various animals, but also plants (willow, birch, etc.) and some natural phenomena (heavy rain, heavy snow, etc.). These animals usually show their own characteristics in the way of human behavior and thinking. It can be said that they are human and beasts, and they usually have relatively fixed personality characteristics and symbolic meanings. For example: the lion is the king of the beasts, he is majestic and powerful, it often represents violent and cruel people; wolf-stupid, greedy; fox-clever, cunning and treacherous; snake-jealous. Crow-wise and business-minded; rabbit-timid; cock-aggressive; bull-hardworking and honest; dog-loyal; horse-trustworthy; donkey-funny. For example, the fairy tale "Glubby Wolf" is mainly famous for highlighting the greed and stupidity of wolves.

One day, the wolf wants to eat something special, so it plans to go outside. It first bumps into a rooster on the road and grabs it. When he was about to eat, the rooster says: "If you eat me with cumin and raw onions, it will be more delicious, and you can enjoy my meat." The wolf believes him easily and leaves to find cumin and raw green onions. As the wolf walked away, the rooster runs away. After bringing the cumin and the raw green onions, the wolf cannot find the rooster. He has to give up

eating the rooster and continues his way. On the way the wolf meets a lamb and then a horse, but the wolf was deceived by them again. The horse said to the wolf: "Before my father died, he left a letter on my leg. This letter is related to you. You can eat me after you read it." When the foolish wolf squatted under the horse's leg, the horse kicks the wolf hard on the head and the wolf dies.

3. Fairy tales about social life

There is a big difference between social life fairy tales and magic fairy tales, which are mainly based on the description of daily life events. The protagonist in such fairy tales is usually a very ordinary person in real life. They achieve their goals through their own efforts and some moral character, so at the ending of the story "they live a happy life." The images of such fairy tales include (yosh yigit) young man, (nuroniy chol) old man, (xasis boy) greedy rich man, (ochko'z, savodsiz qozi) greedy, illiterate judge, (zolim podshoh) cruel king, (berahm qaroqchi) sadistic thieves and so on. For example, "The Tree of Happiness" is a fairy tale about a young man who achieves his goals through his own efforts and some moral character. In order to save the common people who were oppressed by

the cruel king, he brought the leaves of the happy tree for them in order to help the common people live and work in peace and contentment.

The plots of social life fairy tales are relatively simple, and the content is relatively daily. There are no strange and magical plots in magical and animal fairy tales. On the contrary, they always describe some ironic events. They reflect the daily life of the people, family life, and the moral and ethical views and national customs of Uzbekistan.

In summary, through detailed classification and description of fairy tales in Uzbekistan, we can understand the rich national culture and folk wisdom behind the fairy tales. With its playful and humorous language, simple and concise content, and easy-to-understand plot, fairy tales shine in literary works by highlighting the characteristics of national wisdom. As we all know, fairy tales are not only cultural readings for children's enlightenment, but also the records and manifestations of a nation. The colorful Uzbekistan folktales with various literary characters and scenes with different characteristics are integrated into people's daily lives. Shows a vivid picture of Uzbek national style.

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